

Axiom for Zero: Conjugation Properties

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Abstract:

In this article, we have discussed about conjugation property of zero, that seems vividly nonsense, and contradictical, along with Kritima's Equation.

Keywords: Zero, Axiom, Kritima's Equation

Introduction, Results, and Conclusion:

Number Zero, is as fancy, as well as erroneous as it seems, with means of none, but providinh existence of none, allowing us to question about what is none. Let us consider 0 and 0^* be zero and conjugate of zero.

Then as per our Algebraic methods,

$0(\text{zero}) \times 0^*(\text{conjugate of zero}) = 1$, which leads to contradiction, as zero when operates with multiplicative operator, results 0 .

Linear Algebra relies on zero, and unity for variety of purposes, including identity and existence for algebraic expression. And as per Kritima's Equation $0\overline{0} = 1$, we have again attempted to discuss about none, and unity, in terms of Kritima's Equation, where operatorial constant $\overline{0}$ itself, would be an inequality, to discuss about limiting condition for zero to be unit value.

Outcomes:

We shall attempt to discuss this axiom as Axiom of Zero, for further study about Number system and Theories, so that applicablity can be understood.

References:

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